

Retrospective Look at Machine Learning Techniques for Consistent Pattern Recognition

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Abstract

The main goal of example recognition is controlled or unassisted arranging. Of the various structures where pattern recognition is often discussed, this section examines and utilizes 50 relevant evaluations between 2014 and 2020. Recently, brain organizing strategies and approaches derived from quantifiable learning hypothesis have gotten greater attention. Design portrayal, highlight extraction and determination, bunch investigation, classifier plan and learning are some of the difficulties that should be considered while designing an acknowledgement framework. To summarize and examine some of the prominent approaches used in various phases of an example acknowledgement framework, and to identify cutting-edge research subjects and applications in this fascinating and challenging field. Various AI methods have brought pattern recognition systems quicker.

Keywords: Machine learning; neural network; pattern recognition; security; accuracy; classification

1. Introduction

Information Digging includes pre-handling, investigating, and decoding. These include Example Acknowledgement and Machine Mastering. Extraction of examples from data is an example of example Acknowledgement. These methods are commonly linked with image analysis, despite their main usage. Perceptual tasks generally include summarizing data [1]. There are solutions to the Example Acknowledgment issue. The system's AI techniques have been heavily studied. Gullible Bayes classifier, decision trees, and SVM (SVMs). All of these ideologies share a lack of explicit principles [2]. Ai uses directed and unaided order. Classes are pre-portrayed in coordinated characterization. Unassisted request planning chooses classes based on class similarity and predicts data design [3]. Several controlled learning approaches have been utilized to define responses for the example acknowledgement issue [4]. SVM, SVR, K-mean, Boosting, Relapse Tree, and Irregular Woods are widely used [5]. In clinical picture examination projects, a unique approach called Enormous Preparing Counterfeit Neural Organizations (EPCNO) can boost the presentation of Convolution Neural Organizations (CNNs) (MTANNs). There are no high-level semantic constraints for this method [6]. Iris matching with recognition is one of the obvious and solid answers for biometric administrations, alongside face, discourse, handwritten word, and unique mark acknowledgment [7]. Developing frameworks to recognise data patterns is an example acknowledgement. To help complete a work, example acknowledgement software evaluates a scenario in real time. Sensors collect current reality impressions, which a recognition framework organizes or displays. It might be numeric or symbolic. Unify these components with a classifier. The design recognition interface uses various approaches to ensure appropriate sample display. To enhance the pace or precision, a reliable design acknowledgement procedure is necessary. One of the goals of this study is to assess the AI based Example Acknowledgement using recent developments to improve the presentation, precision of the best answers for problems related to data mining and other related fields Table-1 displays different acknowledgment models.

Review on Pattern Recognition

These are basic issues in science, health, advertising, PC vision, AI, and remote sensing. As an example, an unrest is a material that might be named. Consider a distinctive mark, a cursive word, or a human face or a conversation signal.

Table.1. Pattern recognition models

Approach	Representation	Recognition function	Typical criterion
Template matching	Samples, pixels, curves	Correlation, distance measure	Classification error
Statistical	Features	Discriminator function	Classification error
Syntactical structural	Primitives	Rules, grammar	Acceptance error
Neural networks	Samples, pixels, features	Network function	Mean-square error

To categorise the acknowledgment issue, the system organiser either defines or guides the classes based on examples. Biometrics, media database association and retrieval and data mining are only a few of the uses. For predicting instrument wear and recognising instances, D'Addona DM et al (DBC). A common issue with all material removal systems. Weakening of equipment is managed using ANN and DBC processing frameworks. The ANN was configured using DBC and ANN data. As shown, the ANN can predict hardware wear from pre-arranged photographs, while the DBC can recognise similarity/diversity among pre-arranged photos. Complicated issues like ANN and DBC can be tackled later [8]. Table 2: Examples of Acknowledgement Requests By adjusting the low-rankness of the data display and the blunder image, he reported achieving the overall data design and blunder image.

Table.2. Examples of pattern recognition application

Problem domain	Application	Input pattern	Pattern
classes of Bioinformatics	Sequence analysis	DNA/Protein	types of genes/patterns
Data mining	Searching for meaningful patterns	Points in multidimensional space	Compact and well separated clusters
Document classification	Internet search	Text document	Semantic categories
Document image	Blind Reading	Document image	Alphanumeric characters, words
Industrial automation	Printed circuit board inspection	Intensity or range image defective	Compact and well separated clusters
Multimedia database retrieval genres	Personal identification	Internet search	Semantic categories
Remote sensing	Forecasting crop yield	Face, iris, fingerpring	Defective/non-nature of product
Speech recognition	Telephone directory	Multispectral image	Video clip
Speech waveform	Spoken words	operator assistance	Authorized users for control

In both prepared and tested pictures, we seek for barriers in strong face recognition tasks. It was therefore easy to arrange existing regulated data with perfect-code regularisation. Faced with a cluttered face picture, the RDLRR works well. The technique defeated previous cutting-edge facial recognition systems [9]. Iwana BK et al. investigated amazing pathways of action of transitory occurrences using a DTW based DSE. DSE addresses data as dissimilarity vectors. A difference measure was used to embed multiple samples into a vector space. Using big educational files taxed computers. We consider model selection. DSE's vector space allows us to regard its estimates as element determination provisions. To properly group models, this technique requires fewer models. This approach is supported by a handwritten file of online mathematical digits. DSE with bunch organisation enabled 96.67 4.38 percent exactness characterisation with few models [10]. Example identification enhanced DSC disintegration quality prediction by Mage et al. Measurement and item arrangement were predicted. Some atomic building models were also available, which link sub-atomic mix design to degradation-suitable connections. The molecular disintegration apexes were handled and treated with picture handling calculations. Then there was prescient showing inside the instructions [11]. Convolution Neural Organizations (CNN) identify low-level translational invariant provisions, which are subsequently sent off to Multi-Dimensional Long Transient Memory Neural Networks (MDLSTM) for component extraction and learning. The suggested reformist mix of CNN and MDLSTM was tested using the freely accessible Urdu

Printed Text-line Picture (UPTI) dataset. On the UPTI dataset, an affirmation rate of up to 98.12% for 44-classes was refined [12]. To strengthen the investigation, Uhlmann E et al. used another verifiable interaction and sensor information from an SLM machine. SLM was an additional substance delivery measure that has grown in recent years to satisfy client particular needs. Thus, new gathering boundaries have been detected increasing machine sensor counts. So it asks additional information and hassles to do manual data inspection. The findings were analysed utilising a smart device for computing and data analysis [13]. To circumvent the requirement for an explicit element extraction step, Peralta et al. included photo processing into the classifier design. Unique finger impression arrangement was one of the most widely recognised ways to handle revive the ID in massive fingerprint databases. So that a data unique mark could be distinguished from those belonging to the expected class, the request invasion rate was reduced. Characterization generally starts with extracting pieces from the unique finger imprint picture, often including aesthetic aspects. This may be a class for poor fingerprints that was pardoned by normal calculations, like Finger Code. The assessment emphasises the robustness of the arrangement for distinct impressions of a similar unique finger imprint, limiting invasion in the database. In experiments, convolution neural networks outperformed cutting edge classifiers in terms of accuracy and invasion rate.

The tried organisations improved the runtime by improving component extraction and characterisation [14]. An et al. have demonstrated a contactless 3D finger imprint localization framework utilising single shot peripheral projection and bio dot analysis. A person's unique mark is an unalterable and sufficiently gathered biometric. The 3D organic trademark was supposed to produce a 2D image despite the fact that it was 3D. Using peripheral projection, a low force Drove source edifies a finger by grinding it sinusoidally. A CCD camera discovered the fingertip-controlled peripheral design. The 3D finger imprint was redone using Fourier change method based repetition filtering. In the subsequent stage, a non-standard histogram and altered essential limit were discussed for parody finding utilising bio dot examination. The authorised finger test used collimated laser light with internal liquid advancement to generate high mobility bio dot patterns [15]. An overall distinguishing proof framework with progressive order circuits the information of distinct component extractors has been proposed by Peralta et al. Unique mark recognition has been a prominent research topic for years, with different applications and reliably generating individuals to recognise. In such circumstances, the necessity for adaptable, rapid proof frameworks was obvious. In this case, unique mark arrangement was employed to speed up the differentiating evidence.

A component guarantee improved the arrangement correctness. Finally, the classifier's probability organise was used to investigate the classes. A single boundary balances recognised proof time and precision. This method was tested on various NIST databases and a large produced data set, providing entry rates near to the best possible with grouping, low recognised proof times, and almost little accuracy loss [16]. Zeng et al. presented a smart traffic sign recognition method based on assessing the impact of shade spaces on convolution neural framework depiction learning. A DP-KELM was examined using a KELM classifier with substantial perceptual provisions. Traffic sign recognition is critical in autonomous and automated driver assistance systems. Despite the fact that numerous approaches were developed, it was still difficult to obtain high accuracy recognition with cheap computing costs. After adjusting the SPE, a bit-based ELM classifier with excellent computing efficiency and theory execution was available. Specifically, compared to the most precise pivot misfortune stochastic angle drop approach, our strategy achieves a similar acknowledgement rate with reduced computing expenses [17].

Review on Machine Learning

AI is the study of motivating computers to behave without being redesigned. AI has given us self-driving cars, intelligent example recognition, effective web organisations, and an unfathomably updated understanding of the human genome. Various experts agree that it is the best way to get human-level Man-made brainpower. Some of the AI research publications are shown below. The methodology's ongoing sufficiency was evaluated utilising the Spots MIT, MNIST, and a genuine X-ray data source. Situated learning was found to be viable by exploratory results [18]. Olfa has concentrated on the mix of fundamental information and advantageous to

depict an MKL structure for the confirmation of Alzheimer's disease (Promotion). A method for extracting nearby picture obtained biomarkers from Dispersion Tensor Imaging (DTI) and Primary Gentle Intellectual Impedance (SMCI) was proposed in their study. A portion of the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Drive (ADNI) dataset was used to test their technique. The results show that employing a multimodal strategy improved accuracy over performing each technique alone [19]. Zeyad Hailat et al. developed hand-made and Unaided Learning methods to address the Face Recognition Issue. They have shown several ways to trade knowledge. They suggested a Multi-Channel Multi-Model Element Learning (McMmFL) framework to pick discriminative features referring to affirmation problems.

They suggest creating an Auto-Encoder (AE) that combines the Substituting Bearing Technique for Multipliers (ADMM). For the affirmation rates, they recommended using K-implies Grouping and Histogram of Slopes (Hoard). These include AR, Yale, and PubFig83, each with a different affirmation rate [20]. FSSLA) by employing unlabelled models backed by Managed Learning Calculation (SLA) to create the execution of the classifier for the Interruption Location Frameworks (IDSs). The fluffy sum was used to develop low, high, and focus level fluffiness categories using unlabelled samples. Their system was tested on the NSL-KDD dataset. The exploratory results show that unlabelled samples for low and high fluffiness bundles improve classifier performance [21]. Philippe Burlina et al. developed the framework for Utilization of AI Approach utilising Profound Learning for the problem of ARIA and AMD evaluation. They proposed several preferred practise strategies for identifying persons with the broadly appealing sort out fortunately. They've been monitoring the major AMD 4-class, 3-class, and 2-class fierceness requests.

Its suggested structure was tested on the NIH AREDS dataset with 5664 hidden subsidies images, with improved collection problem accuracy for both machine and professional verification [22]. A biomarker of individual variations in the frontal cortex developing interaction, according to James H Cole et al. They suggested a Predictive Demonstrating Approach including Deep Learning, particularly Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs), and both pre-treated and raw T1-weighted data. They verified the CNN mind predicted age accuracy using a large sample of strong adults (N = 2001). They constructed the CNN frontal cortex predicted ages on all datasets using a Gaussian Cycle Relapse (GPR) method. The show was tested using BAHG data. By utilising rough T1-weighted data, the researchers reduced estimate time for new data, bringing the approach closer to delivering continuous information on frontal brain health in clinical situations [23]. This study utilised the Double Tree Complex Wavelet Change (DTCWT-HMT) model for more precise size calcification assurance in cutting edge mammography. Their suggested DTCWT-HMT may get wavelet coefficient connections. They used Hereditary Calculation to enhance DTCWT-HMT and DTCWT (GA). Their projected display employed an ELM, a competent learning speculation, to classify the kind and damaging restricted scope calcifications. The method was tested on the Nijmegen, MIAS, and DDSM datasets using AUC of Recipient Working Trademark (ROC).

The test results showed the suggested technique's accuracy and consistency [24]. Janani Kalyanam et al. concentrated on Non-Clinical Utilization of Prescription Prescriptions/Medications (NMUPD) to build computerised solutions. Disease transmission research (DE). They have aided in assessing the remarkable limited scope contributing to a Twitter blog. From the 11 million gathered tweets, they identified the terrible tweets for regularly mauled arrangement narcotic agony soothing medicines Percocet, OxyContin, and Oxycodone. Unwanted tweets were concluded in three rounds of Solo AI methods. Almost 2.3 million tweets were identified as having content important to reducing NMUPD. A huge data substance mistreatments perception, data social affair, and evaluation component might be employed with various frameworks that rely on content examination and human coding approaches [25]. They employed attractive compasses of metal-hardness offers up particular models in Attractive Transition Spillage (MFL) yields of pipes to depict the blemish types disintegration, breaks, gouges, etc. and assessed the lengths and profundities of disfigurements. They have kept an eye on the human overseer's workload due to the massive amount of data analysed. In their

study, they have supported an automated assessment of MFL signals. Their plan employed PAW to perceive and choose metal-mishap leaves.

Deformations were isolated and the Counterfeit Neural Organizations (ANN) were utilised to examine the importance of the metal-hardship gives up. Finally, their suggested approach was tested using MATLAB mechanical assembly, and the precision was shown [26]. For the characterization of adults through Significant Burdensome Issue (MDD) and Sound Controls, David M Schnyer et al (HC). In their suggested framework, they link the Help Vector AI (SVML) to the MDD vs HC Fragmentary Anisotropy (FA) maps. It was tested using Right Half of the World Entire Cerebrum FA Guide with eight main datasets, and the correctness occurred at explicit particularity and affectability [27]. An alternative model of a Secluded Neural Organization (MNN) is suggested by Sanchez et al. The model's granularity depends on the data base's complexity. In this case, the suggested approach is tested using human recognition based on face data. The ORL and ESSEX face data sets are used to evaluate the suggested method. Four examples are set up to compare with other studies using similar data sets (3 for the Essex Information base and 1 for the ORL Data set). The recommended technique's outcomes are guaranteed to be better than other works' outcomes, based on a factual assessment of findings. The basic idea is to plan measurable neural network topologies using a Progressive Hereditary Calculation (HGA). The distribution of persons in each granule is determined by an inspection, as does the collecting of information [28]. Castillo et al. presented a new streamlining approach for MNN plans using granular registration and a firefly computation. This method is tested with human acknowledgement using benchmark ear and face data banks to assess the strategy's appeal and benefits. There are a lot of improvement techniques nowadays, but find one that works best for your area.

The outcomes achieved for ear acknowledgment and face acknowledgment by the proposed strategy are compared to a progressive hereditary calculation to see which of these strategies gives better results when a secluded granular neural organisation is advanced and applied to design acknowledgment specifically for humans. The amount of modules (or sub granules), degree of information for the preparation stage, learning calculation, objective mistake, number of stowed away layers and their number of neurons are being progressed [29]. Human recognition is carried out by Melin et al. using optimal granulation of information and planning of specific brain organisation structures, and benchmark data sets of ear, iris, and face biometric measurements are used to test and correlate against other studies. The quantity of sub-granules, degree of information for the preparation stage, learning calculation, objective error, number of stowed away layers, and their number of neurons are optimal boundaries of MGNN design. These procedures and tactics have emerged to aid with finding optimal answers for challenges or models and bio-motivated computations are vital for this sector. When applied to human recognition, the results of a dim wolf optimizer are compared to those of hereditary and firefly calculations [30].

4. Review on Pattern Recognition Application

For Symbian phones, Abeni et al. [31] presented a facial recognition system based on one-class BVMs. The evaluation framework was tested on a Nokia 6680 phone, and the results showed that a global limit and a single edge could each achieve an EER of 7.92%. Hadid et al. [32] proposed using Haar-like components with Advertisement aBoost for face and eye location to decompose a face verification graphic. The results were positive and demonstrated the utility of facial recognition on mobile phones. The achieved normal validation rates are 82% for small measured faces (4040 pixels) and 96% for large measured faces (8080 pixels). A low-cost biometric confirmation framework for phones was created by Tao and Veldhuis [50]. Their framework may make 2% errors in the test. Xi et al. [34] suggested a multi-leveled cross-relationship yield top (HCFA) plot for mobile phones that could dissect the link between each sub-locale of a face.

A minimal memory and capacity requirement made the design suitable for a portable registration environment. Their strategy might achieve an EER of 3.58 percent using the Yale Face dataset B. To open the phone,

Findling and Mayrhofer [35] recommended a 180-degree skillet shot of the device around the client's head. They evaluated several assist vector machines and neural networks for face recognition, and the results validated their approach. Chen et al. [36] presented sensor-aided face validation to guard against 2D media attacks and virtual camera attacks. The approach achieved a 95%–97% localization rate and a 2%–3% false alarm rate during 450 preliminary tests in real-world scenarios. Although Rubio et al. [37] shown significant profit in using design recognition to physical neuro-imaging data, little research has been done on how to deduce image features to create the most reliable projections. In this study, Gaussian Cycle AI was used to predict age, sex, and BMI of individuals in the IXI dataset.

Table.3. Comparison analysis for pattern recognition techniques

Reference	Technique	System requirement	Results	Conclusion
NazSetal.[12]	CNN and MDLSTM	MATLAB		
UhlmannEet al.[13]	SLM machine. Nearest Neighbour, Bayes Classifier ,Neural Network, And Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-mean algorithms	CMTtool	TheBayesClassifier,duetothe achievedaccuracyof63%	The result showed that an automatic classification for the SLM machine is possible
PeraltaDetal.[14]	CNN,DNN	Intel Corei7-3820 processor (3.60GHz) and 24GBRAM. The CNNs were run on a single Nvidia Ge Force GTXITANGPU (2688cores,6144MBGDDR5RAM). Database:SFinGe,NIST-DB4	the proposed network obtains 99.60% accuracy	The robustness experiments also showed that the deep learning strategy was able to obtain a very highest accuracy
ChatterjeeAetal.[15]	biospeckle analysis, visuo-numeric algorithm, 3Dsensor, MSF* And non-normalized histogram techniques	MATLAB		Overall the proposed techniques Very simple, fast, low cost and fullfield

5. Conclusion

Discourse Recognition, Text Order, Picture Handling, and Neural Organization Frameworks are examples of related subjects. Its applications include biometrics, bioinformatics, big data analysis, and most recently information science. It is the main features that classify input data. So this study looked at many late Example Acknowledgment Systems using AI. We use AI without even recognising it now. Most AI methods are solo or supervised. On expects individuals to submit facts and forecasts throughout the planning process. The estimator will then apply the findings to new data. The unassisted system should not be ready. Maybe they use Profound Mastering to address problems iteratively. It is used for jobs that are not controlled by AI. In this article, early research in measurable example recognition focused on extracting invariant components. Recently, non-invariant acknowledgment approaches have been planned. These techniques produce minor linear and nonlinear invariance. They are also computationally focused. As a result, Simard et al. developed a digression prop calculation to limit classifier yields. And it's really efficient. In the future, we can employ hybrid AI to improve character recognition and other activities.

5.1 Future Suggestions

Pattern recognition and AI have recently favoured deep neural networks. Face, Handwritten Cursive Word, Discourse Signal, Iris, and Finger Impression Recognition are examples. The AI can assess high dimensional data with measurable features for crop security.

References

- i. Boixader Ibáñez D. Special issue on pattern recognition techniques in data mining. *PatternRecognitLett.*2017;93:1–2.
- ii. Kumar S, Gao X, Welch I, et al. A machine learning based web spam filtering approach. In 2014 IEEE 30th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA), IEEE; 2014.p. 973–980.
- iii. Ermushev SA, Balashov A. A complex machine learning technique for ground target detectionandclassification.*IntJApplEngRes.*2017;11(1):158–161.
- iv. Wu J, Yinan Y, Chang H, et al. Deep multiple instance learning for image classification and auto-annotation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*;2014.p.3460–3469.
- v. Voyant C, Notton G, Kalogirou S, et al. Machine learning methods for solar radiation forecasting: are view. *Renew Energ.* 2017;105:569–582.
- vi. Tajbakhsh N, Suzuki K. Comparing two classes of end-to-end machine-learning models in lung nodule detection and classification: MTANN vs. CNNs. *Pattern Recognit.*2017;63:476–486.
- vii. Aginako N, Echegaray G, Martínez-Otzeta JM, et al. Iris matching by means of machine learningparadigms:anewapproachtodissimilaritycomputation.*PatternRecognitLett.*2017;91:60–64.
- viii. D'Addona DM, Ullah AS, Matarazzo D. Tool-wear prediction and pattern-recognition using artificial neural network and DNA-based computing.*J Intell Manuf.* 2017;28(6):1285–1301.
- ix. Gao G, Yang J, Jing XY, et al. Learning robust and discriminative low-rank representations for face recognition with conclusion. *Pattern Recognit.*2017;66:129–143.
- x. Iwana BK, Frinken V, Riesen K, et al. Efficient temporal pattern recognition by means of dissimilarity space embedding with discriminative prototypes. *Pattern Recognit.* 2017;64:268–276.
- xi. Mage L, Baati N, Nanchen A, et al. A systematic approach for thermal stability predictions ofchemicals and their risk assessment: Pattern recognition and compounds classification basedonthermaldecompositioncurves.*ProcessSafEnvironProt.*2017;110:43–52.
- xii. Naz S, Umar AI, Ahmad R, et al. Urdu Nastaliq recognition using convolutional–recursive deep learning. *Neuro Computing.* 2017;243:80–87.
- xiii. Uhlmann E, Pontes RP, Laghmouchi A, et al. Intelligent pattern recognition of a SLM machine process and sensor data. *Procedia CIRP.*2017;62:464–469.
- xiv. Peralta D, Triguero I, Garcia S, et al. On the use of convolutional neural networks for robust classification of multiple finger print captures.*arXiv preprintarXiv.1703.07270*,2017.
- xv. ChatterjeeA,BhatiaV,PrakashS.Anti-spoof touchless3Dfingerprintrecognitionssystemusingsingleshotfringeprojectionandbiospeckleanalysis.*Opt LasersEng.*2017;95:1–7.
- xvi. Peralta D, Triguero I, García S, et al. Distributed incremental fingerprint identification withreduced database penetration rate using a hierarchical classification based on feature fusionandselection.*KnowlBasedSyst.*2017;126:91–103.
- xvii. Zeng Y, Xu X, Shen D, et al. Traffic sign recognition using kernel extreme learning machines withdeepperceptualfeatures.*IEEETransIntellTranspSyst.*2017;18(6):1647–1653.
- xviii. Afridi MJ, Ross A, Shapiro EM. On automated source selection for transfer learning in convolutional neural networks.*Pattern Recognit.*2018;73:65–75.
- xix. Ahmed OB, Benois-Pineau J, Allard M, et al. Alzheimer's disease neuro imaging initiative, recognition of Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment with multimodal image-derived biomarkers and multiple kernel learning.*Neuro-computing.*2017;220:98–110.
- xx. Aslan MS, Hailat Z, AlafifT K, et al. Multi-channel multi-model feature learning for face recognition.*Pattern Recognit Lett.*2017;85:79–83.
- xxi. Ashfaq RR, Wang X-Z, Huang JZ, et al. Fuzziness based semi-supervised learning approach for intrusion detection system.*InfSci(Ny).* 2017;378:484–497.
- xxii. Burlina P, Pacheco KD, Joshi N, et al. Comparing humans and deep learning performance for grading

- AMD: a study in using universal deep features and transfer learning for automated AMD analysis. *ComputBiolMed*.2017;82:80–86.
- xxiii. ColeJH, PoudelPPK, Tsagkrasoulis D,etal.Predictingbrainagewithdeeplearningfromrawimagingdataresultsinareliableandheritablebiomarker .*Neuroimage*.2017;163:115–124.
- xxiv. Hu K, Yang W, Gao X. Microcalcification diagnosis in digital mammography using extreme learningmachinebasedonhiddenMarkovtreemodelofdual-treecomplexwavelettransform.*ExpertSystAppl*.2017; 86:135–144.
- xxv. Kalyanam J, Katsuki T, Gert Lanckriet RG, et al. Exploring trends of nonmedical use of prescriptiondrugs and polydrug abuse in the Twitter sphere using unsupervised machine learning. *AddictBehav*.2017;65:289–295.
- xxvi. Layouni M, Hamdi MS, Tahar S. Detection and sizing of metal-loss defects in oil and gas pipelinesusingpattern-adaptedwaveletsandmachinelearning.*ApplSoftComput*.2017;52:247–261.
- xxvii. Schnyer DM, Clasen PC, Gonzalez C, et al. Evaluating the diagnostic utility of applying a machinelearningalgorithmtodiffusiontensorMRI measuresinindividualswithmajordepressivedisor-der.*PsychiatrResNeuroimag*.2017;264:1–9.
- xxviii. SánchezD,MelinP.Optimizationofmodulargranularneuralnetworksusinghierarchicalgeneticalgorithms for human recognition using the ear biometric measure. *Eng Appl Artif Intell*.2014;27:41–56.
- xxix. SánchezD,MelinP,CastilloO.Optimizationofmodulargranularneuralnetworksusingafireflyalgorithmforh umanrecognition.*EngApplArtifIntell*.2017;64:172–186.
- xxx. Melin P, Sanchez D. Multi-objective optimization for modular granular neural networks appliedtopatternrecognition.*InfSci(Ny)*.2018;460-461:594–610.
- xxxi. Yan Z, Yiqiang Z, Zhigang P, et al. Multi-instance deep learning: discover discriminative localanatomiesforbodypartrecognition.*IEEETransMedImaging*.2014;35:1502–1343.
- xxxii. Hadida,HeikkilaJY,SilvénO,etal.Faceandeyedetectionforpersonauthenticationinmobilephones. 2007 First ACM/IEEE International Conference on Distributed Smart Cameras; 2007.p.101–108.
- xxxiii. Tao Q, Veldhuis R. Biometric authentication system on mobile personal devices. *IEEE TransInstrumMeas*.2010;59(4):763–773.
- xxxiv. Xi K, Hu J, Han F. Mobile device access control: an improved correlation based face authenticationschemeanditsjavameapplication.*ConcurrComp-PractE*.2012;24(10):1066–1085.
- xxxv. FindlingRD,HözlM,MayrhoferR.Mobilematch-on-cardauthenticationusingoffline-simplifiedmodels withgaitandface biometrics.*IEEE TransMob Comput*.2018;17(11):2578–2590.
- xxxvi. Chen S, Pande A, Mohapatra P. Sensor-assisted facial recognition: an enhanced biometricauthentication system for smartphones. *Proceedings of the 12th Annual International Confer-enceonMobileSystems,Applications,andServices*;2014.p.109–122.
- xxxvii. Monté-RubioGC,FalcónC,Pomarol-ClotetE,etal.AcomparisonofvariousMRIfeaturetypesforcharacterizingwholebrainanatomicaldifferencesusi nglinearpatternrecognitionmethods.*NeuroImage*.2018;178:753–768.